

**ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC HEALTH AS THE MOST IMPORTANT
FACTOR AFFECTING URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY. (IN
THE CASE OF THE NAVOI REGION)**

Abstract. This article discusses the importance of the public health factor in assessing the environmental condition of cities. In particular, the population living in the industrialized Navoi region of our republic and its cities, as well as indicators related to health indicators, were studied. Proposals and recommendations for strengthening public health in the future are given.

Keywords. Human health, industrial cities, mortality rate, chemical substances, death rate, hospitality.

The birth rate, death rate, and morbidity of the population depend on many different reasons, first of all, the age structure, the direct effect of chemical substances on the body, biological, radiation and other factors, as well as the influence of social and psychological conditions in a broad sense.

During the last 10 years, the Navoi region has been distinguished by its average total death rate (average 4.56%) and birth rate (average 22.7%). The following demographic indicators also prove that the region differs from other regions of our republic due to its poor ecological condition.

Total	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Birth	18 067	19 300	20 116	20 259	20 837	20 563	21 595	22 770	23 888	26 576	26 274
Infant mortality under 1 year	138	141	184	199	185	198	149	167	175	186	126
Total death	4153	4103	4188	4110	4401	4472	4161	4378	5038	4848	4156
Natural growth	13,9	15,1	15,9	16,1	16,4	16	17,4	18,3	18,8	21,7	22,1

Table 1. The main demographic indicators of the region in the last 10 years

For the purpose and results of the conducted research, it is important to analyze the health indicators of the population living in regional cities. The available statistical data on the region and its cities for the last five years show that the general morbidity trend in the region is increasing, and we can witness an increase in the overall morbidity index in the cities as well. For example, in 2018,

the total morbidity rate in the region was 508,827, and in 2022, it increased to 519,762 (see Table 2).

Table 2. Total disease rate in regional cities (over the years)

Many socio-economic and ecological factors also influence this. In 2022, the incidence rates of the population in cities are as follows:

The cities of Navoi, Zarafshan, Kyziltepa, Nurota, and Yangirabot stand out in terms of **general morbidity**.

Diseases of respiratory organs - Navoi, Zarafshan, Kyziltepa, Yangirabot cities.

Diseases of the digestive organs - cities of Navoi, Zarafshan, Kyziltepa, Yangirabot.

Eye and eye-related diseases - cities of Yangirabot, Qiziltepa, Navoi.

Diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs and diseases affecting the immune mechanism - cities of Yangirabot, Kyziltepa, Navoi.

Diseases of the circulatory system-Navoi, Kyziltepa, Yangirabot, and Uchkuduq cities.

Diseases of the nervous system - the cities of Navoi, Zarafshan, Kyziltepa.

Table 3. Percentage of major diseases in regional cities.

Many researchers believe that there is a high correlation between the quality of the environment and the morbidity of children because children's bodies are more susceptible to external influences than other age groups.

The highest indicators of the general morbidity of children were recorded in the cities of Navoi, Nurota, and Kyziltepa.

The incidence rate of children under 1 year is divided into a separate group. According to these indicators, the cities of Navoi, Nurota, and Kyziltepa are "leading".

The cities of Navoi (50), Nurota (17), and Kyziltepa (13) differ from other regions in terms of infant mortality.

As for the causes of death among adults, diseases of the respiratory organs (more than 23.8% of all deaths) are in the 1st place, diseases of the circulatory system are in the 2nd place, and diseases of the digestive organs are in the 3rd place. In teenagers, 1- Respiratory diseases (48.6%), 2- Eye diseases, 3- Injury and poisoning. Among children — 1st place — Diseases of the respiratory system, 2 — Diseases of the nervous system and sense organs, 3- Infectious diseases.

In 2022, the situation in the structure of morbidity is as follows:

Elderly population	1. Respiratory diseases 25.9% 2. Circulatory system diseases 13.3% 3. Diseases of the nervous system and sensory organs -11.1%.
Teens	1. Respiratory diseases 48.6% 2. Eye diseases - 10.72% 3. Injury and poisoning - 8.21%
Children	1. Respiratory system diseases 60.4% 2. Diseases of the nervous system and sensory organs 8.7% 3. Infectious diseases - 8%.

Table 4. Incidence structure in 2022 in the cities of Navoi region in 2022..

Compared to previous years, respiratory tract diseases have increased in morbidity in all three age groups. In the cities of the region, where the industrial enterprises are concentrated the most, the percentage of ecologically hazardous productions is high, and the population's morbidity rate is high.

Today, there are 40 hospitals in the region, which is a little less than in previous years (Table 5).

Table 5. Total number of hospitals in Navoi region (between 2010 and 2022)

The life expectancy indicator in the region is also unique. In 2022, the average life expectancy in the region was 76.5 years (Table 6). We can see that this indicator has increased compared to previous years, but as a result of the general management of these statistics at the regional level in our republic, maintaining this indicator in cities should be an important factor.

Table 6. Average life expectancy in Navoi region.

The future of public health depends on developing a holistic approach that addresses many aspects of urban life. For its successful implementation, it requires cooperation between government, urban planners, medical professionals, public organizations and residents. Here are some suggestions and recommendations for developing such an approach:

1. Promote walking, bicycling, and public transportation by improving transportation infrastructure, creating pedestrian-friendly sidewalks, and providing bicycle lanes. This increases physical activity and reduces pollution.

2. Improving educational opportunities, reducing poverty, and providing affordable housing are important factors that affect health outcomes.

3. Providing adequate health facilities and resources to meet the needs of the population, including primary care providers, specialists, hospitals and polyclinics.

4. Improved nutrition during pregnancy, antenatal education, and healthy behaviour during pregnancy are all examples of maternal health promotion. Addressing maternal health problems can significantly lower infant mortality rates.

5. Immunization Programs: Strengthen immunization programs to protect infants from vaccine-preventable diseases. Making sure vaccines are available for all children.

6. Combating Malnutrition: Addressing malnutrition by promoting good nutrition for infants and young children, educating parents on healthy eating habits, encouraging the consumption of nutrient-dense foods, and providing nutritional support to vulnerable populations.

7. Investing in research and innovation: supporting research to develop new technologies that can prevent maternal and child deaths, encouraging health

innovations such as telemedicine and mobile health solutions to reach remote communities.

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